

MANUFACTURING OF HALAL GELATIN: FORMULATION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF GELATIN BASED ON COMPOSITE OF SEA CUCUMBER, SEAWEED AND K-CARRAGEENAN

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Abstract

The study was to examine the characteristics of gelatin produced from the composite of sea cucumber (SC), seaweed (SW), and κ -carrageenan (CR). The formulations used were F1 (100% SC); F2 (50% SC: 25% SW: 25% CR); F3 (25% SC: 50% SW: 25% CR); and F4(50% SW: 50% CR). The characteristics of the gelatin were then analyzed, including viscosity, gel strength, functional groups (with FTIR), and morphology (with Scanning Electron Microscope - SEM); and compared with those of a commercial bovine-based gelatin (CG). The results of the study showed that the highest viscosity was of F4, but the highest gel strength was of F3. FTIR (Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy) analysis showed that all formulas had almost identical spectrum profiles. The highest relative transmittance in the 3300 cm^{-1} region was found in F1, followed by F2 and F3. SEM (Scanning electron microscope) analysis showed that the morphology of F1, F2, and F3 was similar, but significantly different from F4. The addition of seaweed and κ -carrageenan in the resulting halal gelatin formula would be expected to reduce the production costs, so that it might expand its application in various food, medicine and pharmaceutical products.

Keywords: Halal Gelatin, Seaweed, κ -carrageenan, Sea Cucumber.

INTRODUCTION

Gelatin is a protein substance produced through the hydrolysis of collagen which has been extracted from bones, skin, or other organs of mammals (Alipalet *et al.*, 2021; Mikhailov, 2023). Collagen from fishery and seafood products has advantages, such as being free from diseases from poultry and mammals, containing quite high collagen, and halal raw materials (Senadheera *et al.*, 2020; Siburian *et al.*, 2020).

Several studies have been conducted in examining collagen production from fishery and marine products, including from snakehead and patin fish (Baehakiet *et al.*, 2019; Fabella *et al.*, 2018) and from sea cucumbers (Saallah *et al.*, 2021; Tian *et al.*, 2020). Collagen from fishery products has the advantage of being thermostable and having a denser collagen structure (Alfaro *et al.*, 2015; Derkachet *et al.*, 2020; Shi *et al.*, 2022).

One source of collagen as a raw material in the production of halal gelatin is sea cucumbers (*Holothuriascabra*), which are quite abundant in Indonesian waters, including in Southeast Sulawesi (Ansharullah *et al.*, 2020; Ansharullah *et al.*, 2022).

This organism contains quite high nutrients, as well as several functional compounds that are beneficial for health, such as triterpene glycosides, carotenoids, bioactive peptides, vitamins, minerals, fatty acids, collagen, gelatin, chondroitin sulfate, amino acids (Nurilmala *et al.*, 2022; Pangestuti and Arifin, 2018).

In recent years, the health benefits of sea cucumbers have been validated through scientific research and have shown medicinal values such as wound healing, neuroprotective, antitumor, anticoagulant, antimicrobial, and antioxidant. However, there has been no fundamental study on the process of making halal gelatin from sea cucumber collagen.

Currently, the demand for halal food, pharmaceutical, and cosmetic products is increasing globally. One important component of these products is gelatin, most of which (more than 70%) is based on bone or skin collagen from mammals, especially pigs and cows (Alipa *et al.*, 2021).

According to sharia, Muslim consumers are prohibited from consuming products containing pork, or other animals that are not slaughtered in an Islamic manner; and pork and its derivatives are absolutely haram for Muslims (Ahmed *et al.*, 2020; Nurilmala *et al.*, 2022).

Another concern is the possibility of containing bovine spongiform encephalopathy (BSE) or mad cow disease, which is contained in collagen and beef-based gelatin (Nurilmala *et al.*, 2022). Therefore, ingredients from fishery and seafood products have high potential to meet the needs of the Muslim community in terms of the halalness of gelatin products (Ahmed *et al.*, 2020; Nitsuwat *et al.*, 2021; Nurilmala *et al.*, 2022).

This study attempted to utilize fishery products and other marine products in producing halal gelatin. Therefore, the study was aimed to examine the characteristics of halal gelatin produced from a composite formulation of sea cucumber, seaweed and κ -carrageenan.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials

Fresh sea cucumbers were obtained from Leppe Village, Konawe Regency, Southeast Sulawesi, Indonesia. Seaweed flour (*Euchemacottonii*), commercial κ -carrageenan and commercial bovine-based gelatin (CG) were obtained from local markets. All chemicals used for analysis were of analytical grade.

The research consisted of three stages, namely: the first stage (preparation of fresh sea cucumber samples, testing of proximate composition and amino acid profiles as basic information on the raw materials used); the second stage (extraction of gelatin from sea cucumbers using 5% acetic acid with soaking for 48 hours, followed by neutralization with 5% NaOH); and the third stage (making composite gelatin based on sea cucumber (SC), seaweeds (SW), and κ -carrageenan (CR)).

The formulations used were F1 (100% SC); F2 (50% SC: 25% SW: 25% CR); F3 (25% SC: 50% SW: 25% CR); and F4(50% SW: 50% CR).

The characteristics of the gelatin were then analyzed, including viscosity, gel hardness, functional groups (with FTIR), and morphology (with Scanning Electron Microscope - SEM); and compared with those of the commercial bovine-based gelatin (CG).

Proximate and amino acid analysis of the fresh sea cucumber

The proximate analysis, including moisture, protein, fat, and ash were performed according to the method of AOAC (2005). Carbohydrates were calculated as the difference between 100 and the total amount of water, fat, protein, and ash. Meanwhile, amino acids profile of the samples was performed according to the method of Sroyraya et al. (2017).

Viscosity

Viscosity analysis was carried out based on the AOAC (2005). The sample solution was made at a concentration of 6.67% (wet basis). The solution was then measured for viscosity using a Brookfield Synco-Ectric Viscometer. The test was carried out at a temperature of 60°C at a rate of 60 rpm using spindle no. 1, and the result was presented in cP units.

Gel Hardness

The hardness of gel was measured by firstly making a solution of 7.5 g sample dissolved in 105 ml of distilled water. The solution was stirred on a hot plate for 15 minutes at temperature of 60°C, then cooled it for 2 hours at temperature of 10°C. The gel hardness was then tested using a Brookfield CT3 Texture Analyzer at a probe speed of 0.5 m/s, and performed in g bloom units.

Characterization with FTIR spectrophotometer

The functional group of the samples was measured with Fourier transform infrared (FTIR). The test was carried out using the method of Ananda et al. (2018), where the FTIR spectra of samples were obtained from 2 mg of gelatin in 100 mg of KBr (potassium bromide) and placed on the crystal cell of the FTIR spectrophotometer. Measurement was performed at 4000–500 cm^{-1} at room temperature.

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) analysis

The morphology and microstructure of the composite gelatin powder were tested using a scanning electron microscope (SEM) (COXEM, EM-30N User Manual NS 4.1.5 Version, Korea). The surface of dried gelatin was coated with gold in vacuum using sputter coater, and was photographed.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Chemical composition and amino acid profiles of the fresh sea cucumber

Figure 1 shows the proximate composition of fresh sea cucumbers, with the largest component being water at 91.1%. The results of other studies (Abdullah et al., 2013; Asnani

et al., 2019; Elfath et al., 2019) also reported several variations in the chemical content of sea cucumbers. In general, the water content of sea cucumbers is quite high, namely above 80%.

This is because this organism lives and reproduces in full water. Meanwhile, the protein content is around 5%, the ash content, fat content and carbohydrate content are around 1-2%. The variation in chemical content is greatly influenced by the habitat where it lives. The type of carbohydrate contained in sea cucumbers is mostly in the form of glycogen, and does not contain fiber (Maskuret *et al.*, 2024).

Meanwhile, the amino acid profile of sea cucumbers shows the presence of 15 types of amino acids ranging from 0.30-6.63%, as seen in Figure 2. The amino acid glycine has the highest percentage compared to the others, followed by glutamic acid and proline. While the lowest is in the amino acid of histidine.

Figure 1: Proximate composition of fresh sea cucumber

Identification of amino acids also shows that the percentage of the highest amino acid content in raw materials is glycine at 6.63%, glutamic acid at 5.34, and proline at 3.66%.

The high percentage of amino acids, especially the amino acids glycine and proline, indicates that sand sea cucumbers have quite a large potential in producing gelatin.

This is in accordance with Yuswanet *et al.*, (2021) that gelatin is composed of dominant amino acid content including glycine, proline, and hydroxyproline.

Figure 2: Amino acid profiles of the fresh sea cucumber

The presence of several other types of amino acids that have been identified also have quite an important role when consumed by humans. One of the functions of amino acids is their biological function, where amino acids can increase immune tissue, have a positive effect on brain nerve activity, control cholesterol metabolism, stimulate growth hormone secretion, suppress ammonia levels in the blood, help repair significant tissue, and become a fortress from toxic substances that can damage the digestive tract (Li et al., 2007).

Viscosity

As seen in Figure 3, the viscosity of gelatin with the formulation of F1 (100% SC) was 3.67 cP. This value is lower than that of commercial gelatin (CG). In the formulation with the addition of seaweed and κ -carrageenan (F2 and F3), the viscosity increased to 13.60 and 22.27 cP, respectively.

In formulation F4, the viscosity increased significantly to 100.77 cP. This showed that the substitution of seaweed and κ -carrageenan has an effect on increasing viscosity.

The viscosity of *Holothuriascabra* based gelatin (F1) tended to be higher when compared to the results of a study conducted by Ananda et al. (2018) who used *Phyllophorus sp.* sea cucumber with a viscosity value of 1.71 cP. The difference in viscosity values was thought to be caused by the inter and intra-molecular bonds of collagen contained in each material. There were differences in the conformation ability of the triple helix resulting in different

viscosity values (Qiao, et al., 2013). The viscosity value of the gelatin produced was still in accordance with the GMIA standard (GMIA, 2019) which was 1.5 to 7.5 cP. The viscosity of the solution containing seaweed and κ -carrageenan (F2, F3, F4) increased mainly due to its nature as a polyelectrolyte.

The repulsion force between negative charges along the polymer chain, namely the sulfate group, causes the molecular chain to tense, because the hydrophilic nature of the polymer is surrounded by immobilized water molecules, causing the solution to become thicker (Diharmi et al., 2015).

Figure 3: Viscosity profiles of gelatin with the formulation of F1 (100% SC); F2 (50% SC: 25% SW: 25% CR); F3 (25% SC: 50% SW: 25% CR); F4(50% SW: 50% CR); and CG (bovine commercial gelatin)

Hardness of the gel

Figure 4 shows that the gel strength of F1 (100% SC) is lower than the other formulas. By adding seaweed and κ -carrageenan to the formulation, as in F2 and F3, the gel strength increases significantly.

This is in line with the findings of Hauguet *al.*, (2004) who stated that the gel strength of fish-based gelatin is lower than mammalian-based gelatin. As an alternative to mammalian gelatin, fish gelatin might be used as a substitute for gelatin in various needs for food and pharmaceutical products. However, this fish gelatin cannot be directly exchanged with mammalian gelatin due to its low gel strength and low gel formation and melting temperatures. A possible approach to overcome this difference is to mix fish gelatin and marine polysaccharides which produce a system with better gel strength, gel formation, and melting temperatures.

The mixture of fish gelatin and κ -carrageenan would produce solutions and gels with varying levels of turbidity, depending on the polymer concentration, pH, ionic strength, and nature of the added salt.

κ -Carrageenan might increase viscosity and lead to gel formation so that it is used as a stabilizer, thickener, and gel former. The gel formed from κ -carrageenan is thermoreversible and strong. Therefore, it is used as a supporting material for immobilization by entrapment or encapsulation methods.

Figure 4: Gel hardness of gelatin with the formulation of F1 (100% SC); F2 (50% SC: 25% SW: 25% CR); F3 (25% SC: 50% SW: 25% CR); F4(50% SW: 50% CR); and CG (bovine commercial gelatin)

FTIR analysis

The results of gelatin identification using the FTIR spectrum as in Table 1 and Figure 5 shows that all samples have almost identical spectrum profiles. There are significant differences when compared to the spectrum of the control sample (CG). Some differences were the absorption in the 3300 cm^{-1} region.

The highest relative transmittance was found in F1, followed by F2 and F3. In general, the 3300 cm^{-1} absorption was a hydrogen bond between amide and water, so it might be predicted that the water content in F1 was higher. Another unique spectrum was the absorption of the methyl functional group in the 1390s region which was a symmetric & asymmetric bending vibration. It may be suspected that there was a lot of free methyl in F1, and then the structure become looser.

Table 1: Functional group of gelatin with the formulation of F1 (100% SC); F2 (50% SC: 25% SW: 25% CR); F3 (25% SC: 50% SW: 25% CR); F4(50% SW: 50% CR); and CG (bovine commercial gelatin)

Functional Group	Wavelength (cm ⁻¹)	Sample				
		F1	F2	F3	F4	CG
C=O	2200 – 2400	2360	2360	2362	2362	-
Amide A	3300	3370	3361	3335	kecil	3281
Amide-I	1600-1690	1647	1647	1649	1649	1629
Amide-II	1480-1575	-	-	1514	1514	1523
Amide-III	1229-1301	-	1257	1226	1230	1236
Amide-IV to Amide-VI	537-800	712	710 & 570,2	570,2	667 & 567	-
CH ₃	1460-1380	1393	1396	-	-	-

Figure 5: FTIR spectrum of gelatin with the formulation of F1 (100% SC); F2 (50% SC: 25% SW: 25% CR); F3 (25% SC: 50% SW: 25% CR); F4(50% SW: 50% CR); and CG (bovine commercial gelatin)

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) analysis

Microstructure observation conducted using SEM (Scanning Electron Microscopy) was aimed to obtain an overview of the microstructure of the sea cucumber gelatin substituted with seaweed and k-carrageenan, which can be seen in Figure 6. The results of the microstructure analysis show that the F1, F2, and F3 formulations containing sea cucumber gelatin have a similar appearance, with a loose structure. Meanwhile, F4 containing 100% carrageenan, and CG containing 100% bovine gelatin have a compact and dense structure. The compactness and density of the structure in the F4 sample are closely related to its viscosity. Meanwhile, the compactness and density of mammalian gelatin are not related to

its viscosity. This is likely due to differences in the characteristics of the components of the two materials. Carrageenan is a linear chain polysaccharide with a high molecular weight. The polysaccharide chain consists of repeated bonds between galactose groups and 3,6-anhydrogalactose (3,6-AG), both connected by α -(1,3) and β -(1,4) glycosidic bonds (Nurani *et al.* 2024). Meanwhile, mammalian gelatin is obtained through partial hydrolysis of polypeptides of collagen (Ahmady and Samah, 2021).

Figure 6: Micrograph profiles of gelatin with the formulation of F1 (100% SC); F2 (50% SC: 25% SW: 25% CR); F3 (25% SC: 50% SW: 25% CR); F4(50% SW: 50% CR); and CG (bovine commercial gelatin)

CONCLUSION

The halal gelatin produced from the composite of sea cucumber (SC), seaweed (SW), and κ -carrageenan (CR), with various formulas, i.e. F1 (100% SC); F2 (50% SC: 25% SW: 25% CR); F3 (25% SC: 50% SW: 25% CR); and F4(50% SW: 50% CR) indicated that each formula has a different characteristics. The results of the study showed that the highest viscosity was of F4, but the highest gel strength was of F3. FTIR (Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy) analysis showed that all formulas had almost identical spectrum profiles. The highest relative transmittance in the 3300 cm^{-1} region was found in F1, followed by F2 and F3. SEM (Scanning electron microscope) analysis showed that the morphology of F1, F2, and F3 was similar, but significantly different from F4. The addition of seaweed and κ -carrageenan in the resulting halal gelatin formula would be expected to reduce the production costs, so that it might expand its application in various food, medicine and pharmaceutical products.

Conflict of Interest Declaration

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest related to this study.

Author Contributions

All authors have contributed to all aspects of this study, including conceptualization, methodology, data collection, analysis, interpretation, and manuscript writing.

Acknowledgment

This research was funded by the Directorate of Research, Technology, and Community Services, Ministry of Education, Culture, Research, and Technology, Republic of Indonesia, under the scheme of Regular Fundamental Research. We extend our sincere gratitude for their funding support.

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